

A long-term monitoring of micro-tectonic movements in caves at Cape Kaliakra, Northeast Bulgaria: Correlation with seismic events and precipitation

Nikolai Dobrev¹

1 *Geological Institute - Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria*

2 *National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography - Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria*

3 *Faculty of Geology and Geography, Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski, Sofia, Bulgaria*

4 *Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Varna, Bulgaria*

Corresponding author: Nikolai Dobrev (nddobrev62@gmail.com)

Abstract

This article aims to present the results of an 11-year monitoring of micro-tectonic movements along dangerous cracks opening in caves at Cape Kaliakra, Northeast Bulgaria. Two 3D monitoring devices TM71, were installed in two caves, the purpose of which is to monitor the movements of the rock blocks along dangerous cracks. The obtained results of microdisplacement measurements from 2013 to 2023 show active movement along the observed cracks. This is expressed not only in linear trends but also in sudden shifts and short-term shifts followed by recovery (oscillations). The comparison with the local and regional seismicity shows a correlation between the abrupt movements and seismic events along the Batovo fault. Data from the automatic weather station in the town of Kavarna point to a possible link between some oscillation type movements and heavy rainfall in the research area. The results of the analyzes show the importance of long-term monitoring in clarifying the recent geodynamics in the research area. The results obtained provide valuable information about the dynamics of this region, and hence about the geomorphological evolution and the physical-geological hazardous phenomena. The registered movements show the connection between gravitational movements and tectonic ones. For the first time, data obtained through instrumental observations are published, proving the activity of fault structures in this part of Bulgaria. The results can also be used to predict dangerous slope destabilizations, as well as to reduce the risk of their occurrence.

Key words: 3D monitoring, dangerous geological phenomena, geological hazards, karst

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1. Introduction

The clarification of the geodynamics of a given region includes various types of research activities, and obtaining real data on tectonic movements is of key importance. This is achieved by using monitoring techniques, the most common of which are geodetic measurements, and recently remote sensing methods. Since the movement rates are of the order of mm per year, the results obtained are often within the range of permissible error. Another problem is that such

observations have an areal scope, which in most cases does not provide us real values of the movements along the monitored fault.

For these reasons, we used an in-situ method to monitor tectonic micro-movements with equipment installed at specially selected locations (Košťák and Rybář 1978). Such methods have been used in Bulgaria since the 1980s with the installation of monitoring equipment on deep landslides along the Northern Black Sea Coast and active faults in SW Bulgaria (Avramova-Tacheva et al. 1998). A disadvantage of this type of monitoring is the influence of daily and seasonal temperature fluctuations in the massif (Dobrev and Košťák 2000). These influences are minimized when monitoring is carried out in closed spaces such as caves, tunnels, and dam galleries.

Caves represent a relatively conservative environment in which micro-tectonic movements are clearly recorded (Shanov and Kostov 2015). They are also a secure place in which to conduct instrumental monitoring. During the last few decades, the usage of mechanical extensometer gauges for micro-tectonic monitoring has been applied in several caves in the Czech Republic (Briestenský et al. 2011), Slovakia (Briestenský et al. 2007), Bulgaria (Briestenský et al. 2015; Kostov et al. 2018a), Slovenia (Šebela 2016; Šebela et al. 2021), Belgium (Camelbeeck et al. 2012) and Poland (Małkowski et al. 2008). Bulgaria is among the first countries in Europe with instrumental micro-tectonic monitoring in caves, which began in April 1990 (Košťák 1991; Košťák et al. 1998; Kostov et al. 2018b).

The current observations are focused on micro-tectonic movements in NE Bulgaria. This is a relatively unknown region from a geodynamic point of view. The landslide hazard in the area has been studied best. Assessment of the landslide hazard and risk is based on a number of scientific studies (Ivanov et al. 2022; Frantzova 2023; Berov et al. 2024; Frantzova et al. 2024). Cliff erosion affects the coastal zone near Cape Kaliakra (Nankin et al. 2022). Research on the geological evolution of the Black Sea basin has been done by Genov et al. (2024), and data on the level of the Black Sea is given by Ivanov and Dimitrov (2024). The consequences of the seismic impacts of the Vrancea earthquake of 1977 are described by Brankov (1983).

Between 2011–2013, a number of field studies were conducted in NE Bulgaria during the implementation of the MARINEGEOHAZARD project. Using a georadar as well as field research, R. Varbanov (unpublished report, MIS ETC 641 – MARINEGEOHAZARD project) establishes two fault zones that are parallel to the coastal strip between Shabla and Kaliakra, following a direction of 40–45°. He also established fault zones around Cape Shabla with a direction of 110–120°, which for the most part were later confirmed by Rogozhin et al. (2019).

As mentioned above, at the end of 2012, after receiving a signal from the local authorities about cases of collapses around the caves at Cape Kaliakra, a field survey of this section was conducted. As a result of this survey, dangerous overhanging rock blocks were identified in the western part of the cape. At risk were the Historical Museum and a section of the tourist path. The type of deformation was defined as rock toppling. With the cooperation of the local authorities, a decision was made to install two extensometers of type TM71 for monitoring.

In 2017, an additional detailed study of the rock massif in the area of Cape Kaliakra was made. The investigations of the cliff around the headland also included boat surveys, as a result of which a fault was established in the western part, which is located along the cliff, i.e., with a north-south direction. As a

result, rock deformations and the presence of active faults, established with the help of geophysical profiling and field mapping, were established. Fears of a high probability of rockfalls were confirmed after the collapse of the ceiling of The Dark Cave on September 13, 2018.

The magnetometric studies in the regions of Cape Kaliakra performed later in 2016–2018 by a team of the Geological Institute (M. Krastanov, R. Nankin and N. Dobrev), as well as electrotomography, showed the presence of a fault zone crossing Cape Kaliakra in a north-south direction and an almost vertical inclination.

As already mentioned, the section considered is strongly affected by karst processes. For this reason, during the field research, special attention was paid to the karst formations in the area of Cape Kaliakra. The shallow caves along the cliff had been used by the local inhabitants during the Middle Ages (Kostov et al. 2023). The main crack systems formed in the rock massif can be traced on the ceilings and walls of the caves. The local Historical Museum is located in such a cave. Several cracks have been found that cut through the entire massif and have been troubling the museum staff for years. The cracks follow a direction parallel to the direction of the rock slope. One extensometer and one pin mark were installed on two of them.

The research practice at other caves in Bulgaria shows that observations of various physical quantities in karst systems can provide valuable information about the dynamics of processes in depth (Parov 2023; Stefanov et al. 2023). In the current case, the goal is for the information obtained to serve as a basis for comparison with the geological, geomorphological and geodetic data on the movements of the monitored fault structures. In a scientific aspect, this information could help to establish how well the recorded movements coincide with geological and other data, to clarify the mechanism of a given phenomenon, to derive dependencies and influences of various factors, etc., on local, as well as on a regional scale. The accumulated information from the long-term measurements can serve in the predictive assessments of upcoming hazardous geological phenomena at the monitoring point.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Case study area

Two caves situated at Cape Kaliakra are the subject of observation in this study. The site is located about 12 km southeast of the town of Kavarna, Northern Bulgarian Black Sea Coast. The cape is a rocky peninsula extending about 2 km into the Black Sea. The cliff is vertical and rises approximately 60 m a.s.l. It is located on the territory of the historical-archaeological reserve Kaliakra. From a geological point of view, Cape Kaliakra is a rock cliff protruding strongly into the sea, composed of Neogene sediments—calcareous formations, with numerous cave occurrences. These caves were used in the Middle Ages as warehouses for goods as well as for housing, now they are mainly a tourist attraction. In recent years, some alarming trends have been observed in these cave formations, such as collapses and detachment of single rock pieces of various sizes, which endanger the lives of visitors. Some of the collapses occurred during local earthquakes, and others occurred in the spring or late

winter after cycles of freezing and thawing of the massif, but otherwise they were not related to these destabilizing factors.

A survey of the area in 2012 found the presence of fault zones and sections with rock toppling, which is why a decision was made to install a local monitoring system for dangerous cracks threatening the integrity of the rock massif. It includes extensometers type TM71 (Košťák 1991) and pin marks, which were installed in February 2013. The purpose of the current monitoring system is to obtain real data on rock deformations in the studied area. This will provide an idea of the dynamics of the movements, as well as the factors that influence them. The obtained results have practical significance as they can be used in making decisions for countermeasures.

2.1.1. Geological setting

The Black Sea coast in the vicinity of Cape Kaliakra (Fig. 1) is composed of Sarmatian (Bessarabian and Khersonian) limestones. According to the lithostratigraphic division of Popov and Kojumdjieva (1987), they could be related to the Odartsi and Karvuna formations.

At the base of the cliff, limestones of the Bessarabian age of the Odartsi Formation (with a thickness of 16 to 20 m) are exposed. They are mainly composed of foraminifera (*Nubecularia novorossica*) and described by Koleva-Rekalova and Darakchieva (2020). Reef limestones follow further up, and above them, carbonate tempestites (storm sediments) with a thickness of about 25 m (Koleva-Rekalova 2000; Koleva-Rekalova and Dobrev 2019). The Cape Kaliakra section terminates in limestones about 5 m thick, composed

Figure 1. Case study area and the geological setting.

mainly of *Maetra* shells, known as *Maetra Limestones*. Their age is defined as Middle Khersonian, and they are assigned to the *Karvuna Formation*.

2.1.2. Tectonic structure

The tectonic structure of the area is still not well understood. Cape Kaliakra is located within the easternmost part of the Moesian Platform (Dabovski et al. 2002). Although various studies of the tectonic structures in the area have been conducted, there is no accurate model of the tectonic structure of the area until present. A summary of the fault structures in the area given by A. Radulov (unpublished data, MIS ETC 641 – MARINEGEOHAZARD project) provides information on various fault structures and zones, not all of which are proven to be active, as well as with unproven locations and directions. Most of these faults are nameless and their kinematics and exact locations are still under discussion (Fig. 2). These are the Batovo and Kaliakra fault zones, as well as

Figure 2. Scheme of known fault structures with probable activity, established in recent years in the area of Cape Kaliakra (Rogozhin 2019; unpublished data by A. Radulov and R. Varbanov) and epicenters of local earthquakes registered within the period from 1st of March 2013 to 31st of December 2023 with established magnitudes M_p . Abbreviated names of faults: BF–Batovo Fault, IMF–Intramoesian Fault, KF–Kaliakra Fault.

the Intramoesian fault (Dimitrov et al. 2003; Oaie et al. 2016; Rangelov et al. 2019; Rogozhin et al. 2019).

The Batovo fault zone follows an east-west direction (Kuprin et al. 1980). It separates Holocene sediments of variable thickness along the shoreline. It is followed from the Batova river to Cape Kaliakra. Some researchers suggest recent activity of this fault (Kotzev et al. 2001, 2006).

The Kaliakra fault zone is located in the shelf section of the coast. It follows a direction of 20–40°. The width of the fault zone is from 1 to 3 km, and the length is estimated to be about 80 km (Andreev et al. 1981), but according to other researchers (Krastev and Mihova 1990), it is probably longer. The strong earthquake of 31st of March 1901 (M7.2) is associated with this fault zone, whose epicenter is located 20 km east of Cape Kaliakra. The prevailing opinion is that the fault is of the subsidence type with an east-dipping direction (Kuprin et al. 1980). The last stronger earthquake occurred on the 5th of August 2009 (M5.0), during which rockfalls were triggered along the coastline between Cape Kaliakra and Kamen Bryag village.

The Intramoesian fault is a large structure running between the Carpathians and the Black Sea coast. Tectonic morphology associates with two terrestrial sub-parallel branches separated by 5–6 km; they have been followed about 30 km from the coastline (Rogozhin et al. 2009). Most Bulgarian authors do not consider this fault to be active (Vrablianski 1975; Bončev et al. 1982; Kotzev et al. 2001, 2006), while other researchers assume it is a fault activity (Morelli and Barrier 2004). Recent studies of the fault and its outcrops in the field have been done by Rogozhin et al. (2019). The team establishes short segments of it near Shabla and east of it, which, however, are not attached.

2.2. Methodology

The present study involves the use of two TM71 extensometers, which are installed at specially selected locations in two of the caves of Cape Kaliakra. The observations are carried out monthly, visually, and together with them the temperature of the consoles holding the equipment is recorded. This is necessary to eliminate the influence of the thermal expansion of the consoles when calculating the movements.

The selected cracks were identified during field surveys and analyses, as well as additional geophysical profiles. Magnetometric studies confirmed that these structures are traced to a depth of 200 m and are probably of tectonic origin (unpublished data).

For comparison with influencing factors, data from the National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (NIGGG-BAS) for local seismicity, and for precipitation, from local weather stations in the area are analyzed. So far, the precipitation factor has not been subject to comparison and analysis in observations with this type of equipment.

2.2.1. Measuring technique

The monitoring of dangerous geological processes is carried out by means of TM71 type extensometers manufactured in the Czech Republic (Košťák 1991). They allow three-dimensional tracking of slow movements with great

accuracy, up to 10 μm . They are used in monitoring fault movements, collapses, block landslides, as well as deformations in engineering facilities (tunnels, dam walls, etc.).

The extensometer is adapted for constant monitoring of slow movements that could hardly be detected using classical means of observation. The observations are carried out on site, directly at the selected position of a given fault, considering the displacements along the three spatial axes X, Y and Z. The apparatus works on the principle of mechano-optical interference and the related Moiré effect. The displacements along the three coordinate axes are calculated using trigonometric formulas. The device allows periodic resetting after accumulating large displacement values. Registration of displacements is carried out at equal time intervals depending on the dynamics of the observed process. Additional reports are taken after each episodic event (e.g. earthquake) felt in the measurement area (Krastanov 2022).

Research into the TM71 gauge began in the late 1960s in Czechoslovakia (Košťák 1969). The objects of observation are characterized by slow movements, deep landslides, slope creep, rock deformations, etc. Observations are carried out over a long period, often several decades. The registered movements can include both trends (linear or variable), and sudden slips (shifts), as well as oscillatory movements (or impulses, i.e. sharp movements with subsequent partial or complete recovery, see Fig. 3). Analyzing the movements also includes the search for correlations with external factors, such as earthquakes (local, stronger regional), extreme or prolonged rainfalls, as well as human impact.

Initially, this equipment was used to monitor slow landslides or rock deformations, mainly in the territory of the former Czechoslovakia. The first gauges for monitoring of active fault were installed in the Garm region of Tajikistan, where influences from local earthquakes were established (Košťák et al. 1992). Later, devices were installed in SW Bulgaria (Dobrev and Košťák 2000; Dobrev 2011), and later in the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Slovenia, Poland, Italy, etc. (Stemberk et al. 2003; Košťák et al. 2006; Briestenský and Stemberk 2007; Gosar et al. 2011). Anomalies have been detected both co-seismically (Dobrev and Košťák 2000; Briestenský et al. 2007), but also before some regional earthquakes (Shanov 1993; Shanov and Dobrev 1997).

Figure 3. Type of fault displacements (Briestenský et al. 2018) and schematic block model showing all of the fault displacement components registered by the TM71 extensometer.

2.2.2. Monitoring points

The location of the monitoring points is shown in Fig. 4. As mentioned above, the cracks affecting the slope follow the direction of the coastline.

The two observation points are assigned nomenclature numbers K1 and K2. The first one was installed in a crack splitting the Historical Museum (Fig. 5). The cave of the museum has approximate dimensions of 6 × 12 m. The height is about 3 m. The crack is parallel to the cliff and is 1–2 cm wide. It follows a direction of 160–170°, the slope is vertical. Data on the local characteristics of the place where the device is installed is shown in Table 1. The table shows the local designations of the three spatial axes X, Y and Z.

The second extensometer is installed in an elongated karst formation formed along a crack (Fig. 6). It is 0.8–0.9 m wide at the cliff, within 0.5–0.7 m in the massif, and then gradually decreases. It is visible up to 8 m in the massif. It is formed by a fissure parallel to the cliff, with a local direction of 150–170° and a slight inclination of ~80° to the west. The data are shown in Table 1.

Figure 4. Southern part of Cape Kaliakra with the locations of the extensometric points. **A** overview of the area **B** Cape Kaliakra **C** the study area at the southern part of the cape. The monitoring points and caves (B and C) are shown as follows: 1) Historical Museum; 2) the Dark Cave; 3) the cave at the tip of the cape.

Table 1. General characteristics of monitoring points and monitored structures.

Monitoring point	Coordinates	Local crack direction	+X	+Y	+Z
K1	43.3617°N 28.4654°E	162°	Compression	Dextral slip	Uplift of the rock slice (the block on the seaward side)
K2	43.3612°N 28.4657°E	168°	Compression	Sinistral slip	Uplift of the eastern block

Figure 5. Monitoring point K1 located in the Historical Museum. **A** the entrance of the museum/cave and unstable block on the right side **B** the monitoring gauge location **C** the cave of the Historical Museum with the main cracks and the location of the monitoring point.

Figure 6. Observation point of K2. **A** Location **B** Monitoring gauge **C** the cave at the end of the bow: cross-section, longitudinal profile, plan. The location of the extensometer is shown.

3. Results

The results obtained from the monitoring up to this point are shown in tabular and graphical form (Tables 2–6; Figs 7, 8).

The graphs show both micro-movement trends as well as abrupt shifts. Seasonal amplitude fluctuations of the rock massif are also visible, which are most clearly expressed in the X direction. For this reason, we have tabulated the approximate values of the amplitudes (Table 2). In the estimation of the trends, we used arithmetical mean calculations of the change of movements per unit of time, taken over a period of one year (annual rates) (Dobrev and Avramova-Tacheva 1997). The velocity data are shown in Tables 3, 5.

Table 2. Approximate values of the average annual amplitudes of movements caused by the seasonal temperature fluctuations in the rock massif (mm).

Monitoring point	X	Y	Z
K1	1–1.5	~0.2	0.1–0.2
K2	0.4–0.6	~0.3	negligible

Table 3. Velocities of micro-movements established at monitoring point K1 (mm/a).

Period	X	Y	Z
10.05.2013–20.06.2017	-0.125	-0.165	-0.348
09.08.2017–20.12.2023	-0.079	-0.036	-0.073

Table 4. More typical recorded sharp movements at monitoring point K1 (mm).

Period	X	Y	Z
20.06.2017–09.08.2017	–	-0.05	-0.87
12.01.2018–13.02.2018	–	–	+0.19
31.05.2018–20.07.2018	+0.23	+0.18	-0.16
14.05.2019–01.06.2019	+0.67	+0.23	+0.24
12.02.2020–11.03.2020	–	–	-0.40
30.09.2020–14.10.2020	+0.39	+0.38	+0.50
02.11.2021–11.12.2021	+0.35	–	-0.40
20.09.2022–13.10.2022	–	+0.51	–

Table 5. Velocities of micro-movements established at monitoring point K2 (mm/a).

Period	X	Y	Z
01.03.2013–16.06.2013	Strong shrinkage of the crack	Strong right movement on the crack	Sharp uplift of SE block
10.09.2013–13.05.2015	-0.067	-0.023	+0.027
06.11.2015–12.01.2018	-0.004	-0.019	-0.033
30.03.2018–30.09.2020	+0.018	+0.075	+0.020
11.12.2021–20.12.2023	+0.072	+0.117	+0.027

Table 6. More typical recorded sharp movements at monitoring point K2 (mm).

Period	X	Y	Z
16.06.2013–10.09.2013	+0.18	-0.12	+1.09 uplift of SE block
13.05.2015–06.11.2015	+0.20	–	-0.35
30.09.2020–23.10.2020	-0.50	-0.34	–
04.02.2021–14.03.2021	-0.34	-0.53	–
23.09.2021–02.11.2021	-0.32	–	-0.28
13.03.2022–19.05.2022	–	–	-0.15
19.05.2023–16.06.2023	-0.32	-0.71	–

Figure 7. Movements registered at monitoring point K1 in the museum. The red arrows show earthquake events (date, magnitude), blue arrows show recorded large precipitation events.

Figure 8. Movements registered at monitoring point K2 in the cave at the tip of the cape. The red arrows show earthquake events (date, magnitude), blue arrows show recorded large precipitation events.

3.1. Extensometric monitoring results

3.1.1. Crack in the cave of the Historical Museum

Two stages are noticeable at this vantage point. The first is up to the summer of 2017, when a sudden collapse of the rock block from the seaside was detected, and the second is from August 2017 until now. After the sharp movement, the general tendency shows a calming down of the block movements, however, rapid sharp movements accompanied by compensation in the opposite direction are noticeable (Table 4). In the last six years, slower movement speeds have been observed along all three axes, while at the same time sharp movements, especially pronounced along the vertical Z-axis, have become more frequent (Fig. 7; Table 3).

3.1.2. The cave at the tip of Cape Kaliakra

The monitoring shows movements with weaker dynamics compared to the movements registered in the other cave. There are five month-long stages in the movements. They are most clearly expressed in the Y and Z axes (Fig. 8; Table 5). On the X-axis, the movements are difficult to distinguish due to the large values of the seasonal temperature fluctuations in the rock massif. For this reason, it is difficult to make accurate predictions about trends for the observed time period. Along the Y-axis, there is a distinct leftward movement trend (the western block is moving to the south), which is most pronounced since 2018. At the same time, a sinking trend of the eastern block was registered along the Z-axis. For the observed period, there are several sharp movements, some of which coincide in time with seismic events in the area.

3.2. Analysis of destabilizing factors

3.2.1. Seismic impact

The analysis of the registered sudden movements shows that only a part of them can be compared with external influences. According to data from the NIGGG-BAS in the study area (coordinates 43.3°–43.7°N / 28.3°–28.7°E) for the observation period from the 1st of March 2013 to the 31st of December 2023, 18 local events were registered, the strongest of which had a magnitude of 4.2 (Table 7). For example, local seismic impacts were detected in July 2015, with the epicenters of three weak earthquakes located in the shelf area and following the direction of the Batovo fault. One of the registered earthquakes with an epicenter NE of the village of Bulgarevo occurred on the 29th of November 2021 may have influenced the movements at monitoring point K1. The fault structure is sub-parallel to the Kaliakra fault and has not yet been named (Fig. 2). In most earthquakes, however, no connection can be established with the sharp movements recorded at the two monitoring points.

The earthquakes that occurred in the region of Vrancea, Romania, with magnitudes of 5 and above were also analyzed. No correlations or influences on the recorded movements were found at the two points.

Table 7. Registered local earthquakes with magnitudes $M_p \geq 2$ in the research area according to data from the NIG-GG-BAS.

Date (dd. mm.yyyy)	Time (UTM)	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (km)	M_p	Axes with registered impact	
						Point K1	Point K2
09.09.2013	20:23	43.36	28.69	9	2.2		
06.05.2014	14:07	43.49	28.53	20	2.4		
14.07.2014	16:54	43.69	28.68	20	2.0		
03.03.2015	03:17	43.37	28.57	5	2.4		
15.07.2015	08:30	43.34	28.37	28	4.2	X	X, Z
15.07.2015	09:16	43.33	28.33	18	2.0	X	X, Z
15.07.2015	16:59	43.34	28.39	24	2.2	X	X, Z
31.07.2015	08:33	43.35	28.60	13	2.5		
27.01.2016	21:31	43.35	28.59	13	3.5		
21.03.2016	21:19	43.52	28.63	22	2.8		
21.03.2016	21:19	43.55	28.62	20	2.3		
07.01.2017	13:20	43.56	28.55	28	2.4		
28.09.2017	10:51	43.38	28.65	8	2.2	Y	
17.09.2018	15:21	43.69	28.38	17	2.0	Y	
28.11.2019	11:37	43.40	28.69	15	3.3		
22.11.2021	15:29	43.44	28.51	15	2.7	X, Z	
01.04.2022	05:54	43.47	28.43	42	2.0		Z
20.04.2023	07:58	43.58	28.49	10	2.0		X, Y

3.2.2. Precipitation

The precipitation factor plays an important role in the dynamics of rock deformation processes. On the one hand, the water in the cracks creates hydraulic pressure on the blocks in the massif, on the other hand, the physico-mechanical parameters of the rocks are reduced. Clarifying the amount of precipitation required the installation of a TFA Nexus type weather station, which was carried out in the area of Kavarna (12 km NW of Cape Kaliakra). The weather station started collecting data since the 1st of June 2021 (Fig. 9). To analyze the precipitation for the entire studied period (2013–2023), data on the precipitation were also used, which were downloaded daily from the website of the National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology (NIMH 2024).

The average annual rainfall for the period 2013–2023 was 433 mm. Monthly rainfall varies between 23.4 mm (May) and 48.8 mm (January). In the rainfall regime, two maxima are observed—January and July, and the minima are in May and August.

Initial data show some correlations between the amounts of precipitation that have fallen and the abrupt values of the micro-displacements. For K1, these are: December 2021, September–October 2022; for K2, they are: September–October 2021, April 2022 and April–May 2023.

Figure 9. Monthly distribution of precipitation, registered by the weather station in the town of Kavarna, period from the 1st of June 2021 to the 24th of December 2023.

In December 2021, there were two days with precipitation above 20 mm: the 1st of December (21.1 mm) and the 30th of December (22.3 mm). December 2021 was preceded by a prolonged dry period—from the 20th of October to the 1st of December, there were only seven rainy days (with precipitation above 1 mm), but none of them exceeded 10 mm. On the other hand, in December 2021, a significant amount of precipitation accumulated (Fig. 10A), reaching 117 mm.

September 2022 had only one day with more than 20 mm of precipitation—the 3rd of September with 27.6 mm of precipitation, which occurred after a dry period, in July and August 2023 there were only three rainy days—on the 1st of August 2023 the rainfall was 10.6 mm, on the other two days—9th and 25th of July with a total rainfall of 5.3 mm for both days. The cumulative precipitation graph shows a very sharp increase in precipitation, although the 24-hour value is only 27.6 mm (Fig. 10B).

Figure 10. Cumulative precipitation curves. **A** from the 1st of December to the 30th of December 2021 **B** from the 4th of August to the 3rd of September 2022 **C** from the 17th of September to the 17th of October 2021 **D** from the 22nd of March to the 21st of April 2022.

September 2021 was a dry month, with a monthly precipitation of only 5.6 mm. In October 2021, there was one day (the 13th of October) with more than 20 mm (26.4 mm) of precipitation. On the 19th of October, rainfall was 19 mm. The cumulative curve shows 60.8 mm of cumulative precipitation over a 30-day period (Fig. 10C).

On the 21st of April 2022, 22.1 mm of 24-hour rainfall was recorded, following a relatively dry preceding 30-day period. The cumulative rainfall of 39.7 mm was obtained mainly for the last 10 days of the 30-day period (Fig. 10D).

In April and May 2023, there were no days with precipitation above 20 mm. The average monthly rainfall for April 2021 was 51.3 mm, and there were eight rainy days during the month, with the highest 24-hour rainfall on the 12th of April at 14.6 mm. For May 2023, the total monthly rainfall was 22.1 mm, with only 2 rainy days and the highest 24-hour rainfall on the 30th of May (19.2 mm).

4. Discussion

Based on the analyzes of the observational data, we can state that block movements in caves have complex dynamics that are the result of the impact of various factors, such as local seismicity and precipitation. The registered dynamics of the movements are decisive in the development of these karst forms. It is also directly dependent on the slope processes affecting the cliff, as well as tectonic movements and local seismicity. From the 11-year monitoring of the cracks affecting caves at Cape Kaliakra, it can be concluded that some of them are identified as related to the Batovo fault, and also to the unnamed fault between the capes of Shabla and Kaliakra (onshore fault, sub-parallel to the Kaliakra fault). These results are essential for geological hazard and risk assessment in the area of Cape Kaliakra. This gives us a basis for assessing the danger inherent in the size and suddenness of movements of detachment and collapse of large rock blocks above the touristic path.

Observations of the crack in the cave at the Historical Museum showed two stages of movement, with the second stage characterized by a decrease in the dynamics of movements. However, the recorded cases of pulses (oscillation), especially along the Z-axis, are increasing.

In the cave in the southern part of Cape Kaliakra, it was found that the movements at this point show lower movement speeds compared to those recorded in the cave near the Museum. There are five stages in the movements. They are most clearly expressed on the Y and Z axes. Along the Y-axis, a distinct sinistral movement trend (the western part is moving south) is noticeable, which is most distinct since 2018. At the same time, a trend of subsidence of the eastern block was registered along the Z-axis.

5. Conclusion

For the first time in this type of monitoring, the registered micro-displacements are compared with the precipitation situation. It is obvious that precipitation also has an influence on some of the oscillatory movements. Despite the observed synchronization in most cases between the occurrence of heavy rainfall and the values of micromovements in the rock massif, the research period is still not sufficient to give definitive assessments of the relationship between

the phenomena. Organized monitoring in the area should continue, and the new data obtained will allow for an assessment of the results. The initial results of this monitoring give us hope that it is possible to assess the probability of potential negative phenomena (collapses), which, however, will require regular and longer-term monitoring of the destabilizing factors. Observations showed their necessity and significance for the general monitoring of micro-displacements along the identified dangerous cracks, which helps to draw important conclusions in the general assessment of the dynamics of movements taking place in the study area.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

Ethical statement

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Author contributions

Data curation: ND, NN, EO. Formal analysis: ND, KK, OD, NN, EO. Funding acquisition: BB, ND. Investigation ND, KK, EKR, MK, RN. Methodology: ND, KK. Validation: PI, OD. Visualization: PI, ND, KK. Writing – original draft: ND, BB, NN, EKR. Writing – review & editing: PI, BB, NN.

Author ORCIDs

Nikolai Dobrev <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5301-1959>

Plamen Ivanov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7139-7303>

Konstantin Kostov <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2351-8634>

Emil Oynakov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8992-5581>

Nina Nikolova <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5782-7111>

Boyko Berov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4931-4655>

Orlin Dimitrov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5148-6536>

Elena Koleva-Rekalova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3066-9015>

Miroslav Krastanov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0250-0346>

Rosen Nankin <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8146-3614>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.